

Supplementary Materials for

Erratum for the Report “Meta-analysis reveals declines in terrestrial but increases in freshwater insect abundances”

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This PDF file includes:

Materials and methods: additional details on methodology and changes to the results of the sensitivity analyses.

Other Supplementary Materials for this manuscript include the following:

Table S1: changes to all model estimates following the correction of the data

Materials and Methods

The following information has been added to the Materials and Methods section of the paper:

Data collection and selection: first paragraph

'It should be noted that during this exclusion process our aim was to retain all insects and arachnids. Hence, if insects would be excluded along with non-insects (due to selective reporting of only certain insect taxa), we chose to include the non-insects as well.'

Data collection and selection: third paragraph:

'In seven datasets with a variable sampling effort over time, there were some months with more than five samples. In these 30 (out of 55966) cases, we retained the originally reported sampling dates, in order not to have to make exceptions in data processing for these months.'

Model checking:

- We tested for effects of confounding effects of start year, end year and duration of each time-series, but only found weak evidence for a negative effect of end year, suggesting that the estimated slope is more negative in later years. This matches the results of the time slices, in which the estimates for the European terrestrial and the North American freshwater data become more negative over time. We found no effect of either start year or duration the chance that the mean estimate was larger or smaller than zero was less than an 80%.'

Outliers:

'We also checked three models (Realm, Continent and Climatic zone as covariates) for sensitivity to outliers, by running the same model, but excluding 11 datasets that had random slopes outside 1.5 the interquartile distance above or below the quartiles of all random slopes. For the Realm model, the exclusion of outliers reduced the effect sizes for both realms (terrestrial: -0.85%; freshwater +0.36% per year), but there was still strong evidence for a decline of terrestrial fauna. For the freshwater, however, there was now no evidence for an increase (terrestrial CI: -1.43%--0.24% $p = 0.997$; freshwater: -0.39%--1.14% per year, $p = 0.173$). Since most of these outlying datasets originated from North America, there was now only weak evidence for a decline of the terrestrial fauna ($p = 0.909$), but no evidence for a trend for the freshwater fauna ($p = 0.137$). For the Australian, or rather New Zealand's freshwater fauna, as the only remaining dataset, there was now weak evidence for a decline ($p = 0.907$). The strength of evidence for, and direction of, trends for the other continents did not change. In the model for climatic zones excluding outliers, the evidence for a decline for the temperate terrestrial insects remained strong ($p = 0.997$), but there was no longer evidence for a trend for the freshwater realm ($p = 0.182$). The evidence for directional trends in the drylands was now strong in both realms. This shows some overall sensitivity to extreme values in the data, which in most cases reduced the effect sizes, as well as the certainty of the estimates. However, all of these datasets classified as outliers were large, datasets with high temporal resolution and spatial replication, with which long-term trends could be estimated with high confidence. Hence, we regarded them as supplying important information on insect trends and based on our main interpretation on the models that include them. The datasets classified as outliers were: DataSource_ID's: 313, 1261, 1364, 1408, 1423, 1427, 1476, 1477, 1478, 1493, 1503. See table S1 and (36) for more details.'